

Mengenal Researcher Academy

Kursus Online Gratis
untuk Peneliti Pemula dari Elsevier

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dipaparkan di Tips & Trik Mendeley
Sabtu, 27 Juni 2020 | 13.00-16.00 WIB

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ELSEVIER'S FREE E-LEARNING PLATFORM FOR RESEARCHERS

RESEARCH PREPARATION WRITING FOR RESEARCH PUBLICATION PROCESS NAVIGATING PEER REVIEW COMMUNICATING YOUR RESEARCH

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Apa itu Researcher Academy?

Sebuah platform e-learning gratis yang didesain untuk membuka potensi para peneliti pemula.

- Lebih dari **65 modul** pembelajaran
- Lebih dari **100 suplemen** sumber belajar
- Disusun sesuai dengan siklus riset dan publikasi
- Tersedia “Career path”

Research cycle Content library

RESEARCH PREPARATION

- > Funding
- > Research data management
- > Research collaborations

WRITING FOR RESEARCH

- > Fundamentals of manuscript preparation
- > Writing skills
- > Technical writing skills
- > Book writing

PUBLICATION PROCESS

- > Fundamentals of publishing
- > Finding the right journal
- > Ethics
- > Open science
- > Publishing in the Chemical Sciences

NAVIGATING PEER REVIEW

- > Certified Peer Reviewer Course
- > Fundamentals of peer review
- > Becoming a peer reviewer
- > Going through peer review

COMMUNICATING YOUR RESEARCH

- > Social impact
- > Ensuring visibility

Modul dan sumber belajar

- Journal Authors
- Elsevier Webshop
- Journal Finder
- Author Services
- EVISE
- ScienceDirect

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Sekian...

Ada pertanyaan?

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